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Research Article

**PHYSIOLOGICAL BASES IN DEFINITION OF
LEUKOCYTURIA AND ERYTHROCYTURIA**¹Dr. Shahid Iqbal, ²Dr. Muhammad Adil Khan, ³Dr. Muhammad Ali¹MBBS; Rawal Institute of Health Sciences Islamabad, Pakistan. Email:shahid.crystalheart@gmail.com, ²MBBS; Ameer Ud Din Medical College Lahore, Pakistan,³MBBS; Ameer Ud Din Medical College Lahore, Pakistan.**Abstract:**

As a part of leukocyturia and erythrocyturia amount has been utilized to identify renal diseases for a long period. Additionally the observed attributes are the type involving main standards to recognize urinary syndrome. The objective of the research function ended up being to define that the appropriate physiological regimen of kidneys working functioning that enables to fulfill reliability with the circumstances in kidneys along with the blood cells preservation in urine for additional improvement with the urinary disorder symptomatic technique.

Generally we reviewed twenty four healthy participants between the age of 19–25 without medical and clinical signs of kidneys pathology. Research work was performed in the screening from 9–11 while on an empty stomach. The overall investigation strategy incorporated the draining of the urinary bladder subsequently hydrosaline loading was performed per os in volume of 0.5 % from the entire body mass. Within an hour determination that individual under the examination emptied his bladder and the volume of diuresis was determined accurately up to 1 ml. They used photometric approach to discover creatinine concentration by Popper's methodology, also photometric approach was adopted to discover protein quantity as stated by the response with sulfosalicylate acid within the spectrophotometer SF – 46 and urine osmolality applying crioscopic approach on osmometer, model 3D3 expressed by "Advanced Instrument Inc." (USA).

We have additionally accomplished the four-serial examination: with running water loading (1st group) and with natrium chloride solutions loading, 0.1 % (second group), with 0.25 % (third group) and with 0.5 % (fourth group). The attained outcomes were up statistically implementing the Student criteria.

The accomplished data established the fact that running water loading and also the 0.1 %, 0.25 %, and 0.5 % natrium chloride solutions loading significantly increase diuretic level and diuresis volume per 1 min is greater than diurnal diuresis level 2 – 3 times with recount for 1 minute. Generally it has been excreted from 25 % up to 90 % of the intoxicated liquid volume. Withal, diuresis amounts do not fluctuate significantly from each other considering all of loading types. That particular is, the recommended by us amount of hydrosaline loading supplies equivalent diuresis surmounting. Approach of diuresis enhance differs significantly: with water loading kidneys are operating in regimen of urine dissolving the thing that is demonstrated by lowering of urine osmolality to the exact level which happens to be typical of blood plasma and below. Urine osmolality of some tested participants was varying between 120 – 200 mosmol/kg. There is no doubt that such a dynamic causes depression of kidney's concentration capability caused by providing an organism with significant amount of running water, osmolality of that will be not more than 5 mosmol/kg.

In 0.5% body mass volume the Hydrosaline loading with water and 0.1 %, 0.25 % and 0.5 % solutions of natrium chloride preserves diuresis speed retaining within the volume of 2 – 3 ml per 1 min, however varies in urine osmolality amount. After hydrosaline loading with 0.5 % solution of natrium chloride urine osmolality creates physiologically additional optimal circumstances and might be suggested for leukocyturia and erythrocyturia perseverance.

Keywords: Erythrocyturia; Leukocyturia; Urinary syndrome.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Shahid Iqbal,***MBBS; Rawal Institute of Health Sciences Islamabad, Pakistan. Email: shahid.crystalheart@gmail.com.*

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INTRODUCTION:

It happens to be known that assortment options that come with leukocyturia and erythrocyturia were consumed for a long period to identify renal diseases and tend to be the ones major standards to recognise urinary syndrome. As, a principle, there is quantity and quality perseverance with the cell constitution with the regular urine sediments within the base of these test or recognition with the investigation by Nechipurenko or Amburje (Suarta, 2016).

The final ones diverge on, about the cell constitution of urine that will be characterized is accumulated for the reduced period of time, and furthermore leukocyturia and erythrocyturia computation per volume unit is currently being done concurrently concerning the period of diuresis. However, the existing techniques do not let thinking about issues that determine the blood cell's reliability in urine additionally, the identity nature and volume of performing nephrons (Ryan, 2006).

The purpose of the research work would be to define such the appropriate underlying regimen of kidneys performing working that enables to fulfil security of the circumstances in kidneys and the blood cells savings in urine for additional enhancement of the urinary syndrome diagnostic methodology (Suarta, 2016).

METHODS:

There was clearly evaluated twenty four healthier research volunteers at the age of 19–25 with no clinical and laboratory signs and symptoms of kidneys pathology. Research work was performed in the screening from 9–11 on an empty stomach. The overall examination system incorporated the emptying of the urinary bladder subsequently hydrosaline loading was performed per os in volume of 0.5 % based on the body mass. In one hour examinee, that individual under the test emptied

his/her bladder and the volume of diuresis was estimated specifically up to 1 ml.

We applied photometric approach to find out creatinine attention by Popper's methodology, also photometric technique was adopted to discover required protein amounts focus as stated by the response with sulfosalicylate acid on the spectrophotometer SF-46 and urine osmolality implementing crioscopic technique on osmometer, model 3D3 made by "Advanced Instrument Inc." (USA).

We acquired 10 cm³ by means of the total urine volume for 10 min centrifuging it with 1500 revolutions per minutes; the number of erythrocytes and leukocytes was determined in a specific camera device. All data were done of the kidneys functioning indices based on Bradley and Peleshchuk.

We now have additionally performed the four-serial examination: with running water loading (the first group) and with natrium chloride solutions loading, 0.1 % (the second group), with 0.25 % (the third group) and using 0.5 % (the fourth one). The accomplished outcome was up statistically utilizing the Student criteria.

RESULTS:

The accomplished information establish that the running water loading and the 0.1 %, 0.25 %, and 0.5 % natrium chloride solutions loading significantly increase diuretic level and diuresis amount per 1 min surpasses diurnal diuresis level 2 – 3 times with recount for a single minute. Generally it is excreted through 25 % up to 90 % of the drunken liquid amount. Withal, diuresis amounts do not diverge significantly from one another well with all sorts of loading (Méal, 2015). That is certainly, the recommended by us volume of hydrosaline loading provides equal diuresis exceeding (according to given below Table 1).

Index	Water loading	Loading with 0.1 % natrium chloride solution	Loading with 0.25 % natrium chloride solution	Loading with 0.5 % natrium chloride solution
	n ¹ = 14	n = 10	n = 11	n = 24
Diuresis, ml/per hour	174 ± 33	177 ± 37	143 ± 33	158 ± 19
Relative diuresis, %	55.8 ± 11.4	53.8 ± 9.1	43.3 ± 9.6	49.2 ± 6.2
Urine creatinine, mmol/l	7.9 ± 1.5	5.2 ± 1	12.3 ± 3.5	12.5 ± 1.7 p ² = 0.05
Excretion of creatinine, mmol/per hour	1.1 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1	1.8 ± 0.2 p < 0.05
Osmolality of urine, mosmol/kg	379 ± 45	397 ± 81	569 ± 106 p < 0.05	617 ± 58 p < 0.05
Excretion of osmotically active substances, mosmol/ per hour	62.9 ± 11.5	58.3 ± 8.9	56.6 ± 8.1	85.9 ± 9
Standardized excretion of osmotically active substances (mosmol/mmol of creatinine per 70 kg of body mass)	58.3 ± 5.5	84.2 ± 9.9 p < 0.05	78.5 ± 20.1	56.7 ± 3.2

¹n – number of observations

²p – true index of differences in comparison with water loading.

Table 1: Functional urine condition of healthy volunteers at water and hydrosaline loading in 0.5 % of the body mass (X ± m).

(Source: Méal, 2015)

Though, the procedure of diuresis enhance varies significantly: with water loading kidneys are operating in regimen of urine liquefying something demonstrated by reducing of urine osmolality towards the level that will be usual for blood plasma and below. Urine osmolality of certain examined participants was varying amongst 120–200 mosmol per kilogram. It is obvious that this type of vibrant trigger anxiety of kidneys' density capability caused by supplying an organism with significant amount of running water, osmolality of that will be not significantly more than five mosmol per kilogram (Méál, 2015).

Essential here to mention that the diuresis identity was altering with hydrosaline loading, so, after loading with solutions of growing up focus of

sodium chloride: urine osmolality evolves frequently and achieves the highest point when implementing 0.5 % solution of sodium chloride (See Table 1). In the backdrop of the authentic elimination enhancing of creatinine the presented fact exhibits that there happening switching from tubular into glomerular (more historical phylogenetically) regulation level.

In line with our objective and targets it is essential to mention that within fourth group the urine of all volunteers was hyperosmotic, that is, its osmolality exceeded 300 mosmol per kilogram (Minakova and Bagdasarova, 2017). Correspondingly, while erythrocyturia and leukocyturia it has been stated that the amount of blood cells in 1 cm³ of urine was min in the 1st group and an average rising was 50 % in the 4th group (See Table 2).

Index	Water loading	Loading with 0.5 % natrium chloride solution
	n ¹ = 18	n = 23
Diuresis, ml/per hour	174 ± 33	158 ± 19
Osmolality of urine, mosmol/kg	379 ± 45	617 ± 58 p ² < 0.05
Erythrocyte amount in 1 ml of urine	1097 ± 27	1576 ± 34 p < 0.05
Leukocyte amount in 1 ml of urine	639 ± 45	978 ± 33 p < 0.05
Protein of urine, mg/l	9 ± 1	15 ± 1 p < 0.05

¹n – number of observations

²p – true index of differences in comparison with water loading

Table 2: Leukocyturia and erythrocyturia indices of healthy volunteers after water loading and loading with 0.5 % sodium chloride solution in volume of 0.5 % from the body mass. (X ± m).

(Source: Minakova and Bagdasarova, 2017)

At our sight that is not so much due to increase of erythrocytes and leukocytes penetrating into urine as conditions' optimization of their safety maintenance.

Thus as osmotic lysis of erythrocytes starts in solutions corresponding to 0.5 % solution of sodium chloride, which osmolality according to our

measurements is equal to 160 mosmol/kg, it is possible to make a prognosis, that with osmolality of urine more than 200 mosmol/kg (considering considerable portion of carbamide in urine osmolality formation) osmotic lysis of erythrocytes and leukocytes decreases considerably. It is supposed logically that increase above 400 mosmol/kg point by urine osmolality, practically is a guarantee from blood cells lysis in urine according to osmotic mechanism (Minakova and Bagdasarova, 2017).

Further increase of urine osmolality could lead to cells shriveling due to their dehydration. However, it doesn't produce the cell lysis with this, more of it – while microscoping they appear more visible. Individual analysis of leukocyturia and erythrocyturia after water loading without natrium is its confirmation. Thus, 3 under the test volunteers™ have diuresis that increases up to 365 ml/per hour, and urine osmolality fluctuates between 160 – 270 mosmol/kg, that is the urine was hypotonic. All these patients have no defined erythrocytes and leukocytes in urine. Whereas, after hydrosaline loading of the tested volunteers their diuresis was between 160 – 190 ml/per hour, osmolality 307 – 440 mosmol/kg and there were defined erythrocytes and leukocytes in all probes (Minakova and Bagdasarova, 2017).

DISCUSSION:

It happens to be known, that urine osmolality with the entrance to the distal nephron section contacting isoosmolality, and additional on passing through luminal fluid along complicated an important part of distal tubules and relating duct, urine concentration or its dilution take place, and owing to that particular urine turns out to be hypotonic or hypertonic. Besides, as it is simple to assume, that urine index pH might severely do something about blood cells protection in situations of spontaneous diuresis that will be varying extensively (Gozhenko et al., 2012).

At that moment, the recommended and advised by us approach licenses to deal with neutral pH index of urine. On the base the previously listed reasons we give consideration to that optimal situation for understanding leukocyturia and erythrocyturia is microscopic research of the urine cellular elements

following hydrosaline loading with 0.5 % solution of natrium chloride in volume 0.5 % of the body mass (Chambers, 2013).

CONCLUSION:

1. Hydrosaline loading in 0.5 % amount of body mass along with water and 0.1 %, 0.25 % and 0.5 % solutions of natrium chloride preserves diuresis speed keeping with the volume of 2–3 ml per 1 min, however varies in urine osmolality volume.
2. After hydrosaline loading with 0.5 % solution of natrium chloride urine osmolality creates physiologically more optimal circumstances and might be suitable for leukocyturia and erythrocyturia perseverance.

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